

CRIMINAL LAW PROTECTION OF PERSONAL INFORMATION SECURITY

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The security of personal information is an important aspect of modern life, as more and more personal information is stored and processed electronically. Personal information includes any data that can be used to identify a person, such as their name, address, social security number, or financial information. The security of this information is crucial because it can be used for identity theft, fraud, or other criminal activity. Criminal law provides protection of personal information, and this protection is becoming increasingly important in the digital age[1].

The criminal law protection of the information security of personal information involves the use of criminal law to prevent, investigate and punish crimes against the information security of personal information. The criminal law system provides a framework for the identification and prosecution of persons engaged in criminal activities that endanger the security of personal information[2]. The legal protection of personal information security includes various legal measures such as criminal sanctions, administrative sanctions and civil liability[3]. Legal protection of personal information is necessary to ensure the confidentiality and security of people's personal information and prevent unauthorized access to it[4].

Criminal law protection of personal information security is of great importance in modern society. The protection of personal information is necessary for the functioning of many modern systems, including financial systems, healthcare systems and government systems[5]. Criminal law protection of the security of personal information provides the basis for ensuring the security of these systems and protecting people's personal information[1]. The evolution of the criminal law doctrine and legislation aimed at protecting the information security of the individual is analyzed, and the author identifies information security as an independent object of criminal law protection[6]. In general, criminal law protection of the security of personal information is crucial to ensure the confidentiality and security of people's personal information, as well as to prevent criminal activity that jeopardizes the security of personal information[4].

One of the most common criminal offenses related to the security of personal information is the theft of personal data[7]. This crime involves the unauthorized receipt of someone's personal information, such as name, social

security number, or financial data, with the intention of using it for personal purposes. Theft of personal data is punishable under administrative and criminal law, while the Criminal Code provides for an independent norm of this offense. Theft of personal information can lead to significant financial losses and damage to a person's reputation.

Cybercrime and cyberbullying are another criminal offense related to the security of personal information[8][9]. These crimes include harassment or intimidation of a person through the use of electronic means of communication or social media. Cyberbullying and cyberbullying can have serious consequences for the mental health and well-being of the victim and can even lead to physical harm. The problem of illegally obtaining personal data is becoming more and more urgent, and this crime is often associated with the "appropriation of the identity" of another person[10]. The theft of personal data can be carried out in various ways, including through hacking and cyber espionage[11].

Hacking and cyber espionage are also criminal offenses related to the security of personal information[11]. These crimes include unauthorized access to computer systems or networks for the purpose of stealing or manipulating data. Hacking and cyber espionage can cause significant damage to individuals, organizations, and even governments. Protecting personal information from such crimes requires the adoption of reliable cybersecurity measures, including the use of strong passwords, firewalls and antivirus software[12]. Criminal law protection of personal information security is a complex and developing area of law that requires interdisciplinary approaches that take into account both legal and sociological aspects[13][2][14][15][6][2][16][17][18].

The protection of personal information is regulated by laws and regulations aimed at protecting human rights to privacy[19]. The Federal Law "On Information, Information Protection and Information Technologies" operates with the concepts of presentation and dissemination of information[20]. Information protection involves the adoption of legal, organizational and technical measures to protect information from unauthorized access or disclosure[21]. The basic rules for processing personal data are reflected in Law No. 152-FZ "On Personal Data", and penalties are provided for violations of the law[22]. The issue of legal regulation of professional secrecy is also raised by the Law "On Information, Information Technologies and Information Protection"[23].

In cases of violation of the security of personal information, criminal liability may be imposed on the persons or organizations responsible for the

violation[2]. Liability for violation of the law on personal data includes fines for citizens, officials and legal entities[24]. The criminal law protection of personal data is crucial in ensuring the security of the state, protecting the life, health, dignity and honor of citizens[4]. However, criminal legislation needs to be modernized to enhance its effectiveness in terms of criminal law protection of information security[25].

In addition to legal measures, it is important to inform and educate the public about the importance of personal information security[19]. Information dissemination and awareness campaigns can help people understand the risks associated with disclosing personal information and take the necessary precautions. The media can play a vital role in informing the public about cases of violations of the security of personal information and the legal consequences of such actions[26]. By promoting public awareness and education, people can more actively protect their personal information and contribute to creating a more secure online environment[1].

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